

Financial Health Analysis with the Help of Different Metrics

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ABSTRACT:

To accurately evaluate the financial health and long-term sustainability of a company, a number of financial metrics must be considered. Four main areas of financial health that should be examined are liquidity, solvency, profitability and operating efficiency. However, of the four, likely the best measurement of a company's health is the level of its profitability. There are a number of financial ratios that can be reviewed to gauge a company's overall financial health and to make a determination of the likelihood of the company continuing as a viable business. Standalone numbers such as total debt or net profit are less meaningful than financial ratios that connect and compare the various numbers on a company's balance sheet or income statement.

Keywords: Financial health, Profitability, Balance Sheet, Financial Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION:

Financial health analysis (FHA), as the word says, is how to determine the financial health of a company. The analysis is primarily performed by the management of companies to assess the business sustainability. Financial health is a term used to describe the state of company's monetary affairs. There are many dimensions to financial health, including profitability, liquidity, solvency, operating efficiency, working capital, inventory turnover, accounts receivable turnover, accounts payable turnover etc.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

1. N. SABARISUDHA (2011-13): The author study of financial performance evaluation by ratio analysis at VYSYA Bank project report submitted to university of madras. In which author uses various ratios to evaluate the financial performance as well as operational performance of the bank.

2. Gangadhar (1998): Has made an attempt on “Financial Analysis of Companies in Criteria: A Profitability and efficiency focus” one of the objectives of the study is to analyze the liquidity position of the companies and to point out the factors responsible for such a position. It is concluded that the liquidity position was quite alarming since these are facing chronic liquidity problems.

3.OBJECTIVES THE STUDY:

1. To recognize the financial strength and weakness or position of the business.
2. To analyses the operating cash flow of company.
3. To analyze the solvency of company towards its long term debt obligations.
4. To analyze the profitability and liquidity of the business with the assistance of net profit ratio and gross profit ratio.
5. To recognize the liquidity position of the business with the use of current ratio
6. To assess the working proficiency of the firm.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Type of Research Used:

Descriptive Research:

Type of research is used for this project is Descriptive research. Descriptive research is defines the characteristic of the population or phenomenon, that is begin examined. This methodology focus on what of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject.

Sources of Data:

Secondary data highlights the background understandings for primary data collection. It provides rich understandings into the research process.

Secondary data is collected with the help of following sources:

- Profit and Loss accounts statements. (P&L A/C)
- Balance sheet (assets and liabilities)

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

(A) PROFITABILITY:-

1] Gross Profit:

$$\text{GROSS PROFIT RATIO} = \text{GROSS PROFIT} / \text{SALES} * 100$$

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
GROSS PROFIT	13,69,93,055	24,50,52,654	33,02,61,215
SALES	48,41,62,126	60,76,07,621	68,42,21,948
RATIO	28.29	40.33	48.26

INTERPRETATION:

Generally, the higher the gross profit margin the better. In this company Gross Profit ratio for the year 2017 is 28.29%, for the year 2018 is 40.33% and in the year 2019 it is 48.26%. So, it is interpreted that gross profit ratio from last few years is increasing and it at satisfactory level. So, at the end it indicates that company is growing and financial health is good.

2] NET PROFIT RATIO:

$$\text{NET PROFIT RATIO} = \text{NET PROFIT} / \text{SALES} * 100$$

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
NET PROFIT	1,19,34,966	8,77,54,383	10,70,54,612
SALES	48,41,62,126	60,76,07,621	68,42,21,948
RATIO	2.4	14.44	15.64

INTERPRETATION:

In the year 2017 Net Profit ratio is 2.4 % and in the 2018 net profit ratio is 14.44% and in the year 2019 it is 15.64 %. Generally a 10% net profit margin is considered average, a 20% margin is considered high (or “good”), and a 5% margin is low. In this company Net Profit in 2017 is not good, which is very low, but in next years it again goes on increasing it shows that company is growing and now its financial health is good.

B] OPERATING CASH FLOW RATIO

Operating Cash Flow RATIO = OPERATING CASH FLOW / NET SALES *100

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
OPERATING CASH FLOW	11,68,52,159	22,43,53,924	31,22,65,310
NET SALES	48,41,62,126	60,76,07,621	68,42,21,948
RATIO	24.13	36.92	45.63

INTERPRETATION:

Operating cash flow indicates whether a company can generate sufficient positive cash flow to maintain and grow its operations, otherwise, it may require external financing for capital expansion.

For the year 2017 ratio is 24.13%, for the year 2018 the ratio is 36.92 % and for the year 2019 the ratio is 45.63 %.In this company operating cash flow ratio is

goes on increasing, it company is generating more cash from its operation to meet its short liabilities as well as its daily expenses.

C] LIQUIDITY RATIO:

1] CURRENT RATIO –

$\text{CURRENT RATIO} = \frac{\text{CURRENT ASSETS}}{\text{CURRENT LIABILITIES}}$

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
CURRENT ASSETS	8,86,14,083	14,02,89,304	18,96,17,120
CURRENT LIABILITIES	10,88,30,468	9,50,51,146	8,74,75,493
RATIO	0.81	1.48	2.17

INTERPRETATION:

Current ratio indicates company's ability to pay its short term obligations with its current assets. In the year 2017 the ratio is 0.81%, in the year 2018 the ratio is 1.48% and in the year 2019 the ratio is 2.17 %.

In the year 2017 the ratio is 0.81 % it indicates that company is having more current liabilities than current assets, so it shows company's inability to pay off its obligations in this year. But from 2018 current ratio is greater than one it means company developed its ability to pay off its short term obligations.

D] SOLVENCY RATIO:

SOLVENCY RATIO = NET INCOME + DEPRECIATION / SHORT TERM DEBT + LONG TERM DEBT

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
NET INCOME	1,24,72,627	8,79,54,652	10,83,12,016
ALL LIABILITIES	16,80,31,828	12,14,57,788	12,50,98,624
SOLVENCY RATIO	7.42	72.41	86.58

INTERPRETATION:

Generally, a solvency ratio of 20% and higher is considered to be good. In this company the solvency ratio for the year 2017 is 7.42 %, for the year 2018 the ratio is 72.41% and for the year 2019 the ratio is 86.58 %

In the year 2017 the ratio is lower it indicates that company is unable to pay its long term debt obligation, but from the year 2018 the company developed its ability to pay off its long term debt obligations. And since 2018 solvency ratio is increasing.

D] WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER RATIO:

WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER RATIO = NET SALES / WORKING CAPITAL

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
NET SALES	48,41,62,126	60,76,07,621	68,42,21,948
WORKING CAPITAL	-2,02,16,385	4,52,38,157	10,21,41,626
RATIO	-23.94	13.43	6.69

INTERPRETATION:

Working Capital is the difference between current assets and current liabilities. So, to calculate working capital ratio we divide net sales by working capital, but in the year 2017 working capital is negative because of higher current liabilities than current assets.

In the year 2017 the ratio is -23.94 %, in the year 2018 the ratio is 13.43 % and in the year 2019 the ratio is 6.69 %. Positive working capital turnover ratio is better but in 2017 it is negative and from 2018 and 2019 the ratio is positive so it is interpreted that in the year 2018 and 2019 company's financial health is good.

EJ INVENTORY TURNOVER RATIO:

INVENTORY TURNOVERR RATIO = COST OF GOODS SOLD/AVERAGE INVENTORY

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
COST OF GOODS SOLD	34,71,69,070	36,25,54,989	35,39,60,711
AVERAGE INVENTORY	3,51,50,684	5,06,79,536	6,21,42,424
RATIO	9.87	7.15	5.69

INTERPRETATION:

Higher INVENTORY TURNOVER RATIO is the good sign of better inventory management. But ideal inventory turnover ratio is 4 to 6.

In this company the inventory turnover ratio for the year 2017 is 9.87 %, for the year 2018 ratio is 7.15 % and for the year 2019 the ratio is 5.69 %. These ratios are almost near ideal ratio, except for the year 2017 which higher i.e.9.87 %. So from this ratio it interpreted that the financial health of company is good.

F] RETURN ON INVESTMENT RATIO:

$$\text{RETURN ON INVESTMENT} = \text{NET PROFIT} / \text{INVESTMENT} * 100$$

PARTICULARS	Jan - Dec 2017	Jan - Dec 2018	Jan - Dec 2019
NET PROFIT	1,19,34,966	8,77,54,383	10,70,54,612
INVESTMENT	15,91,87,893	19,36,78,237	22,83,93,710
RATIO	7.49	45.30	46.87

INTERPRETATION:

Always higher return on investment is better. Higher return means higher profitability from the project.

In this company the ratio for the year 2017 is 7.49 %, in the year 2018 the ratio is 45.30 % and in the year 2019 the ratio is 46.87 %. So, return on investment is positive as well as it is increasing from the year 2017 to 2019. Return on investment is at satisfactory level. So, it is interpreted that company's financial health is good.

6. FINDINGS:

- 1) Foresight CFO Pvt. Ltd. Has current ratio bigger than one, except in the year 2017. It specifies that the firm is having current assets higher than current liabilities.
- 2) Company's Net Profit ratio is also bigger than one it indicates that the business is having sufficient net profit from its activities and company's financial health is good.
- 3) Gross Profit ratio is also at satisfactory level from the year 2017 to 2019, it indicates that the company generates sufficient income from its business.
- 4) Company's Solvency ratio is also higher; it means company is having ability to pay off its short term as well as long term debt obligations.
- 5) Company's working capital Turnover ratio in the year 2017 is negative because of in this year company has more current liabilities than current assets. But from the year 2018 it is positive, so, it shows that the business will not have financial issue in future course of action.
- 6) Company's Inventory Turnover Ratio is positive it shows that company is having proper inventory management. The Inventory Turnover Ratios are almost near to ideal ratio.
- 7) Company's inventory turnover ratio is higher and it goes on increasing, it shows that company is generating more profit from its operations and financial health of company is good.

7. CONCLUSION:

- 1) Company Profitability ratios like Net Profit Ratio and Gross Profit Ratio both are higher and are at satisfactory level, so it is concluded that company's financial health is good.
- 2) Company's Liquidity Ratio and Solvency Ratio both are at satisfactory level so it is concluded that company is having ability to pay off its short term as well as long term debt obligations.
- 3) In the year 2017 Working Capital Turnover ratio is negative but from 2018 it is positive as well as satisfactory, so it concluded that initially company's financial health is not good but right now it is good as well as it is improving.
- 4) Company's Return on Investment is higher, so it concluded that company is generating sufficient cash from its operation and financial health of company is good.

8. REFERENCES

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